

FEATURES OF MEANS OF EXPRESSION OF RESPECT IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation This article discusses the features of the means of expressing respect in the Uzbek language. It also examines the views and opinions of Uzbek scholars and researchers on the means of expressing the meaning of respect in the Uzbek language, the phenomenon of translation, as well as the object of communication.

Key words: respect, behavior, ethical thinking, values, dignity, human qualities, justice, humanity, upbringing, thoughtfulness, greeting etiquette, words of wisdom

O'ZBEK TILIDA HURMAT MA'NOSINI IFODALOVCHI VOSITALARNING XUSUSIYATLARI

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“Jahon tillari va adabiyoti” kafedrasini o'qituvchisi

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilida hurmat ma'nosini ifodalovchi vositalarning xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, o'zbek tilida hurmat ma'nosini ifodalovchi vositalarni tahlil etishda ushbu tilda mavjud, murakkab jarayon hisoblanmish hurmat ma'nosining mavjud yoki mavjud emasligi, uning o'рни, tarjima hodisasi, shuningdek, muloqot ob'yekti ekanligi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Hurmat, xulq, ahloqiy fikrlash, qadriyatlar, izzat-nafs, insoniy fazilatlar, adolatparvarlik, insonparvarlik, tarbiya, andisha, salomlashish odobi, hikmatli so'zlar.

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА СРЕДСТВ УВАЖЕНИЯ В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются особенности средств выражения уважения в узбекском языке. Также рассматриваются идеи и взгляды узбекских ученых и исследователей на значение уважения в узбекском языке, феномен перевода, а также объект коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: уважения, поведение, этическое мышление, ценности, достоинство, человеческие качества, справедливость, человечность, ospитание, вдумчивость, приветственный этикет, слова мудрости

The concepts of "respect" and "behavior" the intensification of social life and the complexity of the content of social relations require the training and education of the younger generation.

A person and his consciousness are closely connected with the concepts of "respect" and "behavior" during human activity. A person is formed, polished and grows in the process of various activities.

A number of researches and studies in Uzbek linguistics are based on these requirements. One of the researches in this direction is a comprehensive study of the meaning of respect in the Uzbek language and the features of its expression. To date, the meaning of respect in Uzbek linguistics has not been studied as a separate, independent category. Some linguists, including A. Gulomov, Sh.

Sh. Sadykova explores the means of expressing respect as a "category." The study of the opposition of respect and disrespect in the occurrence of the category of respect has led to a detailed analysis of its methods, classifying the meaning of respect genetically, dividing it into genuine respect and relative respect.

Khodzhiyeva uses the term "field" based on a term that means a broader concept of respect than the grammatical category. Based on the term grammatical category, subsequent tools are again overlooked. This is not in line with the essence of the system

approach. From this it is understood that it is expedient to study respect on the basis of a broader concept than the grammatical category. In linguistics, the word field is used for this purpose. The term was first used in Germany in the 1920s and introduced into Soviet linguistics by Germanists in the 1960s. This term is not alien to the Uzbek national thinking. It was used in the 15th century by our great ancestor Alisher Navoi; *Not easy to stand in this area*. The study of linguistic phenomena in Uzbek linguistics based on this began in the 80s.

In addition, the means of expression of respect in various fields have been studied by the following researchers H.K.Imamova, A.Gulamov and others in the analysis of works of art in different areas: Scholars have given different definitions to the category of respect from different angles. "Respect can be seen as an element of moral thinking." - Graham.

In 1944, A. Gulomov was one of the first to think about the meaning of respect in the Uzbek language, and spoke in detail about the meaning of respect with the plural suffix of the horse. In the 50s and 60s of the last century, some morphological means of respect, including possessive affixes, NK Dmitriev, EV Sevortyan, AN Kononov, Yo. Scholars such as Nazarov have also touched on this issue in their works.

In addition 1991, B. Yusupov in his monograph *"Mestoimeniya v starouzbekskom literaturnom yazyke"* (XV-XVI vv) spoke about the peculiarities of the expression of the meaning of honor in the context of rhymes. In addition, in 1969, K.E. Maitinskaya commented on the use of diamonds in languages of different systems about the aspects of respect semantics related to rhymes. In 1980, M.S.Uzina stopped short of expressing respect for some rhymes in Persian. D. Hakimov's article *"Lexical and semantic features of the pronouns you and you"*, written in 2003, complements the existing ideas about the expression of the meaning of respect in the Uzbek language through pronouns.

Respect is a forbidden thing, a sacred thing; sanctity, inviolability; honor, respect; ink respect for someone or something, a sense of glorification; applied in such emotional relationships.

The meaning of verses 23-24 of Surat al-Isra in the Qur'an is as follows: If one or both parents are elderly in your presence, do not say "ugh" or shout at them. Speak softly to them! Be humble to them! *"Lord, have mercy on them because they raised me in my youth!"* bless them.

Abu Nasr al-Farabi writes, *"Plato explained the need to distinguish between the essential qualities of human nature and their opposites. He explained that ... if a person achieves his goal and earns respect, but achieves the goal in a crooked way, it is also harmful."* This means that everyone should strive to achieve the goal in an honest way, with hard work and earn respect. Only a person with a pure and pure heart respects the rights of others, treats everyone equally and sincerely. When people go to another

country, they should respect and follow the language, religion, customs and order of the local people. Such an attitude is a sign of respect for the people of this country and means respect for the culture and values of other nations. For example, in a Muslim state, it is natural for locals to be dissatisfied with a girl or a boy wearing tight, short clothes, as this is not in line with national customs and culture.

From time immemorial, both in the East and in the religious and philosophical teachings of the West, through moral concepts, "*What is the essence of man, what spiritual criteria does he rely on in his relations with others?*" They tried to find an answer to the question.

Husayn Waz Kashifi says: "*Ten signs of respect, decency and morality*":

The first: - goodness,

Second: - to be honest,

Third: - not to blame anyone else,

Fourth: - If a person sees something wrong, start him on a good path,

Fifth: - If a person confesses his guilt and apologizes, accept the apology,

Sixth: - to take on the burden for others,

Seventh: - not to pursue only self-interest,

Eighth: - to be open-faced, sweet-spoken,

Ninth: - to meet the needs of the needy,

Tenth: - to put his respect in place with politeness and humility.

As these thinkers say, respectful behavior is such a mirror that not only a person's appearance but also his inner world is visible. The level of inner perfection is evident in the humility, politeness, thoughtfulness, and shyness that can be observed from the outside.

Aristotle says: "If the feelings of thought, morality and respect are pure, but the mind that judges them is misleading, there is no room for virtue. Because virtue comes from pure feelings with a mind that leads to goodness. Therefore, if a person has a virtue, it is impossible to use it for evil purposes.

Therefore, these rules cannot be considered as "*small business*". Man cannot make mistakes in affairs. In doing so, he must rise above the various petty ideas and think of the ideas that are more important than them. If a person does not have an intellect, his morals will be superficially artificial: you will not see his humanity as long as you see that he is a human being. It is narrated in the Pearls of Wisdom: "*From whom did you*

learn manners?" they asked. Luqman replied, "I have learned manners from obscenity, and I have refrained from what I accept in their actions!"

Even if you say a joke to a sane person

He draws hundreds of conclusions from it.

But if you teach a fool hundreds of rules

It all seems like a joke to him.

In addition, Yusuf Hos Hajib's work "*Qutadg'u bilig*" was chosen as one of the important sources in the interpretation of the category of respect of the ancient Turkic peoples. In the life of the Turkic peoples, the book "*Kutadg'u bilig*" seeks a rational solution to the problems of society through advice, proverbs and sayings that cover the society - language and culture and are based on them. The integral connection of these rings at the same time reflects the culture of the individual. If this connection between them is lost, the power of speech will disappear by itself. This tradition is important not only for the 11th century but also for today.

Qutadg'u Bilig aims to show that the category of respect is linguistically good not only in verbal form, but also in nonverbal (paralinguistic) terms. In the study, the possessive suffix "-im" is based on linguistics with the pronouns "you", "you" and the verbs "enter", "exit"; It is explained using examples of the formation on a paralinistic basis with the symbols "hand", "foot", "bass", "earth", "sefer kosesi", "bass kose".

At the same time, Yusuf Hos Hajib's "*Qutadg'u Bilig*" reflects all aspects of respect, which is the highest criterion of human relations. When Yusuf Hos Hajib says "respect", he means moral perfection with the greatest qualities. After all, a morally perfect person is the primary basis of all life and activity. The poet writes in particular:

"When a person has good manners and morals, he achieves his goals and happiness makes him laugh, because good morals are the basis of all goodness."

Let's say a person plants a tree and digs a pool. He has another life that belongs to his children, brothers and sisters, relatives, and will never die, so it is not doomed to be forgotten at the time of his burial. Kindness to small, helpless insects and animals is also a great virtue.

If you are a smart cat, kind,

So, you are healthy, says Khusrav Dehlavi.

The ancestors took a piece of bread that had fallen to the ground, gently rubbed it on their faces and eyes, and lifted it from the bottom of their feet to the edge, where it would be eaten by birds and dogs and cats. The same has been said of paper. Throwing bread, paper on the ground, crossing it was considered a sin. The same can be said of

water life. It was feared that if a person, large or small, urinates in water, it is a great sin and he becomes blind. The waters of lakes, rivers and streams were therefore clean, pure, sweet.

An important pedagogical work of Muhammad Sadiq Qashqari on respect and morality is the book *"Odob as-salihin" (Etiquette of good people)*. The content of this work testifies to the fact that it is a remarkable moral and educational work. The scholar explained the purpose of writing this work as follows:

In this sense, Mahmud Kashgari also noted that the plural form expresses respect. He writes that the Turks used the word *sen* to refer to minors, servants, and people who were lower in rank, career, or age than the speaker. They called you people who were more respected than themselves. The Oguzs, on the other hand, use *you* as the elder and *you* as the younger. Many have used it as well.

If you are great, be kind,

It's a good idea to have a good one.

Purpose: When you find a degree or a career, make your character beautiful; be a benefactor to the rulers, a good receiver of the affairs of the people.

Here, in all the works of Alisher Navoi, human respect for each other is described as an important treasure. The thinker considers etiquette to be the most important criterion of respect. Being polite and moral helps a person to gain a certain position and respect among those around him. Alisher Navoi expresses the following views:

"Adab gives young people the blessings of the elders and began to enjoy the prayer movement for a lifetime.

Politeness instills the love of the little ones in the hearts of the great, and that love stays in the heart forever. "

The great poet made a great contribution to the upbringing of a young, mature and harmoniously developed generation with his respectful and thoughtful views on education. Thoughts on universal qualities are very important for our time.

That is why Alisher Navoi's *Mahbub ul-Qulub (Love of the Hearts)* focuses on this topic. The first part of the work deals with the character and condition of different categories of people; the second part is good verbs and bad verbs; and the third part consists of the appearance of various benefits and narratives, i.e., allegories of good verbs and qualities.

Who in the way of truth has taught you a letter with a ranj,

It is impossible to turn around with his true face.

The science of etiquette is also taught by teachers. Therefore, respect for teachers is both a duty and an obligation for students.

There are many ways to honor people in Islamic cultures around the world. For example, kissing the hands of parents, grandparents, and teachers is recommended. It is also narrated in the hadiths of Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him):

"Whoever looks at the faces of his parents and teachers with a smile will be rewarded by Allah with success and happiness."

Language has a social character in society, and it is a means of connecting people, of exchanging ideas, of the interactions that occur in the process of social labor. It is also one of the important symbols of the spiritual image of the nation, an invaluable mirror of human thought.

"If bad behavior becomes a habit," Ibn Sina said, "it will lead to customer misbehavior." For example, anger is intensely heated, grief is strongly debilitating, and frustration loosens the lustful energy and makes the client prone to phlegm. As a result of temperance, both the breath and the body become healthy. "

In addition, Hazrat Abdullah Avloni wrote: *"To bring up a child well for his health and happiness is to keep his body clean, to correct his youth, to teach him good manners, and to protect him from bad manners. Educators are like doctors, just as a doctor treats a disease in a patient's body, so education should be given to a child who is "cleansed" by a treatment called "writing behavior".* After all, we are commanded to correct our behavior according to the commandment *"Hassinu akhlakakum"*. But the main claw of our good behavior is upbringing.

One of the scholars said: *"The happiness of every nation, the peace and prosperity of states depend on the good upbringing and respect of young people." In Islam, it is obligatory for fathers to educate their children in writing, and it is obligatory for fathers to educate orphans of their own nation ... "*

From ancient times, our ancestors, who have always respected the woman who is the source of human life under the feet of heaven, have made it easier for women to run for household worries, daily chores. As a delicate creature, they avoided any hard work and were in the service of the female breed.

One of the main qualities is to be a highly spiritual person, it is not an innate quality of a person, but the gift of destiny determines a person's humanity. After all, the great and honorable name "MAN" is accessible and worthy of spirituality.

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